

Kinetics of substitution reactions of hexacoordinate cobalt(III) complexes with phenoxyacetic acid herbicides

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Abstract : Phenoxy herbicides are proved to be potential chelating agents in the metal complexation showing substitution reactions following second order kinetics. The reactions of $cis-[Co(en)_2(H_2O)_2]^{3+}$ with a series of substituted phenoxyacetic acids proved to be biomolecular and second order rate constants ($\log k''$) values are found to be linearly dependent on the Hammett substituent constants (σ) of respective phenoxyacetic acids. The high value of regression coefficient ($r = 0.82$) indicates that reactivities of these herbicides depend on number, nature and position of substituent group in the benzene ring. Further, the kinetic and thermodynamic stability of these complexes are also interpreted on the basis of equilibrium and rate constant data. The rate and equilibrium constants, spectral changes and their linear correlations with Hammett substituent constants (σ) for both biologically active and inactive phenoxyacetic acids are of comparable magnitudes, thereby ruling out the possibility of chelation as a possible mode of action of these herbicides.

Keywords : Phenoxyacetic acid, herbicides, chelation, Hammett equation, buffer solution, Henderson's equation.

A plenty of literature¹⁻³ is available on the existence of metal ions in biological systems bound (complexed) with biologically important molecules (biomolecules) like proteins or in the form of metalloproteins and metalloenzymes.

Phenoxyacetic acid herbicides have been reported to form stable solid metal complexes which are characterized by three dimensional X-ray structure analysis^{4,5}. Biological systems involve many chemical and biochemical equilibria involving metal ions, metalloenzymes, metalloproteins, etc. In the present work, it is postulated that the application of a phenoxy herbicide may cause imbalance in these enzymatic equilibria either by forming true complexes or complexes of some sort involving biomolecules⁶⁻¹⁰. Thus, in order to explore the mode of action of phenoxyacetic acid herbicides^{7,11}, the model metal complex species like $cis-[Co(en)_2(H_2O)_2]^{3+}$, has been selected for the study of its interaction with a series of phenoxyacetic acid herbicides¹²⁻¹⁵. The kinetics of ligand substitution reactions of this species have been studied spectrophotometrically at 30 °C and in 60% (v/v) dioxan-water system at pH value of 4.6 to evaluate the possibility of ternary metal complexation processes and mechanism of mode of action of herbicides.

Materials and methods :

All chemicals were of A.R. grade. The ligands were obtained direct from Fluka AG, Buchs, Switzerland and were used after further purification. All the solutions were prepared in 60% (v/v) dioxan and carbonate free double distilled water. A digital pH-meter model 101E was employed to record the pH values. All spectral measurements were made with a Bausch and Lomb spectronic-20 spectrophotometer.

The complex $cis-[Co(en)_2(H_2O)_2](NO_3)_3$ was prepared by standard method¹⁶. A 30 ml aqueous solution containing 4 g of $l-[Co(en)_2(CO_3)]I$ was shaken with 20 ml aqueous solution containing 1.86 g of $AgNO_3$. After removing silver iodide by filtration, the filtrate was mixed with alcohol and crystallized. The solid mass was washed with alcohol and dried. This salt (3 g) was reacted with 15 ml of 3 N ice-cold nitric acid and when evolution of CO_2 was complete, a mixture of equal volumes of ethanol, ether and acetone was added. The resulting red oil which crystallized on adding methanol was collected, washed with acetone and dried over calcium chloride. It was characterized by its elemental analysis and UV spectrum which exhibited maximum absorptions at 360 nm ($\log \epsilon = 1.81$) and 495 nm ($\log \epsilon = 1.90$).

In *aq* + *organic* solvent mixture several *acid-base* and *cis-trans* equilibria are possible. The equilibrium in acid solution (pH 4.6) is strongly displaced in favour of the *cis*-ion i.e. in acid solutions of diaquo salt, less than 2% is to be found in *trans*-ion, while neutral and basic solutions contain about equal amounts of *cis*- and *trans*-complex in equilibrium¹⁷.

In the present investigation, therefore, the medium being acidic, the *cis*-form is the main reactive species.

Ammonium salts of phenoxyacetic acid and substituted phenoxyacetic acids were used in the kinetic measurements of ligand substitution reactions.

Reaction between cis-[Co(en)₂(H₂O)₂](NO₃)₃ and NH₄L (L⁻ = phenoxyacetate or substituted phenoxyacetate anion) :

The solution of complex-A nitrate and NH₄L was taken in 1 : 1 molar ratio and concentrated on a water bath, a sticky mass was formed. This on prolonged digestion with anhydrous ethanol followed by its evaporation at room temperature yielded the product of composition [Co(en)₂(H₂O)L](NO₃)₂.NH₄NO₃. All these mono-substituted products were characterised and found to be of the *cis*-variety through UV-spectrophotometric analysis¹⁸.

The possibility of the formation of 1 : 3 complex with L⁻ has also been explored and it was found that *m*-hydroxyphenoxyacetate and *m*-nitrophenoxyacetate form, respectively, red and yellow crystals of composition [Co(en)₂L₂]L at room temperature on mixing the concentrated solutions of complex-A nitrate and NH₄L in the molar ratio 1 : 3. These products were characterised to be of the *cis*-variety following the UV-spectrophotometric method. However, in cases where L⁻ = *p*-hydroxyphenoxyacetate, *m*-methylphenoxyacetate or *p*-methoxyphenoxyacetate ions, the 1 : 3 solution mixture did not yield crystals at room temperature.

In these cases the solution mixtures were heated at water bath and then cooled in refrigerator to get red crystals of [Co(en)₂L₂]L. The products containing *p*-hydroxyphenoxyacetato and *m*-methylphenoxyacetato moieties were found to be of *trans*-variety. It could not be possible to characterise the product of 1 : 3 composition containing *p*-methoxyphenoxyacetato moiety as *cis*- or *trans*-, because it was insoluble in water at room temperature (soluble in water near boiling point) and hence the solution UV-spectrum could not be obtained. This product may be anticipated to be of *trans*-form based on the observations for similar systems¹⁸, where it was found that the *cis*-product may get isomerised into *trans*-form on heating.

Kinetic measurements :

A reaction mixture of equal volumes of 0.01 *M* solution of complex-A nitrate and a 0.1 *M* solution of NH₄L (1 : 10 molar ratio) was used to maintain pseudo-first order condition. The compositions of the complexes formed were obtained spectrophotometrically using the Job's method. Under the pseudo-first order condition, the maximum in the Job's curve in each system corresponded to 1 : 1 complex [Co(en)₂L(H₂O)]²⁺. Higher complexes could not be identified in this dilution range because no shift in the maximum in the Job's curve was obtained at 1 : 1 molar ratio.

Results and discussion

Interpretation of kinetic data :

The results of the analysis of all the 1 : 1 and 1 : 3 products and electronic spectral data are reported in Table 1. Reactions between the complex *cis*-[Co(en)₂(H₂O)₂]³⁺ and NH₄L [L⁻ = phenoxyacetate, *p*-OH, *m*-OH, *m*-NO₂, *m*-CH₃ and *p*-OCH₃ phenoxyacetate ions) were studied in 60% dioxan (v/v) at pH 4.6 and at 30 °C by measuring absorbance at 360 nm. A remarkable difference was observed in the spectra of the complex *cis*-[Co(en)₂(H₂O)₂]³⁺ and its *mono*-substituted products *cis*-[Co(en)₂L(H₂O)]²⁺. In acidic medium (pH = 4.6) ligands exist mainly as HL persisting the following equilibria in solution :

[NH₄L] was kept high but it provided low [L⁻] at pH = 4.6, which practically remains constant throughout the reaction due to buffering action of NH₄L.

Table 1. Analytical data of 1 : 1 and 1 : 3 products obtained by the reaction of complex nitrate with NH₄L

NH ₄ L	Complex : Ligand ratio	Formula of the complex as per analysis	Analysis		λ_{\max} (nm) in 60% dioxan-water mixture ^b
			Calcd.	Obsd. ^a	
Ammonium phenoxacetate (L = phenoxacetate)	1 : 1	<i>cis</i> -[Co(en) ₂ (H ₂ O)L](NO ₃) ₂ .NH ₄ NO ₃	Co 10.69 N 20.29	10.38 19.02	380 (102.5) 520 (93.6)
	1 : 3	<i>cis</i> -[Co(en) ₂ L ₂]L	Co 9.34 N 8.86	9.30 8.52	380 (115.2) 520 (154.6)
<i>p</i> -Hydroxyammoniumphenoxacetate (L = 4-OH-phenoxacetate)	1 : 1	<i>cis</i> -[Co(en) ₂ (H ₂ O)L](NO ₃) ₂ .NH ₄ NO ₃	Co 10.39 N 19.72	10.34 19.56	370 (202.2) 520 (101.8)
	1 : 3	<i>trans</i> -[Co(en) ₂ L ₂]L	Co 8.68 N 8.24	8.66 8.26	370 (305.0) 560 (116.4) and a flat maxima at 470 (62.4)
<i>m</i> -Hydroxyammoniumphenoxacetate (L = 3-OH-phenoxacetate)	1 : 1	<i>cis</i> -[Co(en) ₂ (H ₂ O)L](NO ₃) ₂ .NH ₄ NO ₃	Co 10.39 N 19.72	10.32 19.06	370 (250.6) 520 (88.6)
	1 : 3	<i>cis</i> -[Co(en) ₂ L ₂]L	Co 8.68 N 8.24	8.70 8.16	360 (172.6) 530 (71.4)
<i>m</i> -Nitroammoniumphenoxacetate (L = 3-NO ₂ -phenoxacetate)	1 : 1	<i>cis</i> -[Co(en) ₂ (H ₂ O)L](NO ₃) ₂ .NH ₄ NO ₃	Co 9.88 N 18.76	9.72 8.80	360 (494) 520 (136.5)
	1 : 3	<i>cis</i> -[Co(en) ₂ L ₂]L	Co 7.69 N 7.30	7.72 7.28	360 (782.2) 520 (114.2)
<i>m</i> -Methylammoniumphenoxacetate (L = 3-CH ₃ -phenoxacetate)	1 : 1	<i>cis</i> -[Co(en) ₂ (H ₂ O)L](NO ₃) ₂ .NH ₄ NO ₃	Co 10.42 N 19.79	10.44 19.82	360 (128.8) 560 (127.6) and
	1 : 3	<i>trans</i> -[Co(en) ₂ L ₂]L	Co 8.75 N 8.31	8.72 8.34	360 (115) 560 (92.8)
<i>p</i> -Methoxyammoniumphenoxacetate (L = 4-OCH ₃ -phenoxacetate)	1 : 1	<i>cis</i> -[Co(en) ₂ (H ₂ O)L](NO ₃) ₂ .NH ₄ NO ₃	Co 10.14 N 19.24	10.16 19.26	a flat maxima at 470 (37.6) 520 (113)
	1 : 3	<i>trans</i> -[Co(en) ₂ L ₂]L	Co 8.17 N 7.76	8.05 7.78	Spectrum could not be taken because of insolubility
<i>p</i> -Chloroammoniumphenoxacetate (L = 4-Cl-phenoxacetate)	1 : 1	<i>cis</i> -[Co(en) ₂ (H ₂ O)L](NO ₃) ₂ .(NH ₄ NO ₃) ₂	Co 10.06 N 19.10	10.02 19.08	350 (340.2) 510 (126.4)
	1 : 3	<i>cis</i> -[Co(en) ₂ L ₂]L	Co 8.02 N 7.61	8.04 7.56	350 (694.4) 510 (96.3)

^aThe observed value of %Co and %N both are lower than the corresponding calculated values because complexes are hygroscopic and there remains some moisture in them.^bThe values given in the parentheses are the molar absorbance indices (extinction coefficients in L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹).

In spite of being low $[L^-]$, but being constant, the forward reaction of eq. (2) may be considered to be pseudo-first order with respect to the complex (A); and, accordingly, the value of pseudo-first order rate constant (k_{obs}) was estimated spectrophotometrically at 360 nm graphically by making $\log (D_\infty - D_0)/(D_\infty - D_t)$ against time (t) plots, where D_0 , D_t and D_∞ are the absorbances in the beginning, after time t and at infinite time, respectively. The value of D_∞ was calculated from ϵ -values of the 1 : 1 complex (B) at 360 nm. The pseudo-first order rate constant (k_{obs}) is quantitatively related to the second order rate constant k'' as follows :

$$k_{obs} = k'' [L^-]$$

$$\text{or } k_{obs} = k'' \cdot Ka \frac{[HL]}{[H^+]} \quad (3)$$

where Ka is the dissociation constant of HA. The effect of the variation in k_{obs} with pH was also studied and it is concluded that a linear correlation exists between them (Table 2). This fact is also supported from above relation (3).

Primarily Irving and Rossotti method¹⁹ was used to evaluate the values of Ka for phenoxy acids (HLs) in

Table 2. Variation of rate constants (k_{obs}) with pH of the medium in 60% aq. dioxan (v/v)

[Complex] = 0.005 M, [ligand] = 0.05 M, $t = 30^\circ\text{C}$

Acid	$k_{obs} \times 10^5 \text{ (s}^{-1}\text{)}$	
	pH = 4.6	pH = 6.0
Phenoxyacetic acid (PAA)	1.58	2.65
<i>p</i> -OH-PAA	2.17	6.17
<i>m</i> -OH-PAA	1.51	1.25
<i>m</i> -NO ₂ -PAA	0.75	0.92
<i>m</i> -CH ₃ -PAA	1.88	5.01
<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ -PAA	2.35	4.74
<i>p</i> -Cl-PAA	1.35	1.10

Table 3. The values of the various constants for the reaction of $cis\text{-[Co(en)}_2\text{(H}_2\text{O)}_2\text{]}^{3+}$ with phenoxyacetic acids in 60% eq. dioxan (v/v)

[Complex] = 0.005 M, [ligand] = 0.05 M, $t = 30^\circ\text{C}$, pH = 4.6

Substituent	Substituent constant (σ)	pKa	$k_{obs} \times 10^5$	$k'_{obs} \times 10^5$	$k'' \times 10^5$ (mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)
			(s ⁻¹) of [NH ₄ L] = 0.05 M	(s ⁻¹) of [HL] = 0.05 M	
-H	0.00	4.43	1.58	2.51	1.31
<i>p</i> -OH	-0.37	4.48	2.17	2.58	3.27
<i>m</i> -OH	+0.12	4.40	1.51	2.63	0.98
<i>m</i> -NO ₂	+0.71	4.25	0.75	2.34	0.25
<i>m</i> -CH ₃	-0.80	4.45	1.88	2.38	1.36
<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	-0.27	4.44	2.35	2.80	2.74
<i>p</i> -Cl	+0.23	4.40	1.35	2.26	0.83

60% (v/v) dioxan solution (Table 3). The values [HL] at pH under consideration were calculated in all the cases using Henderson's equation.

Combining (1) and (2) the resulting equilibrium is

It is necessary to maintain [HL] constant for evaluation of k_{obs} for the above composite reaction. It is not practically feasible to keep [HL] constant by keeping [NH₄L] constant since Ka values for phenoxy acids (HLs) are different. In the first series of experiments described above, [NH₄L] was maintained constant at 0.05 M, so that [L⁻] also remains constant for any system of phenoxy acid. The values [L⁻] were estimated to be different for different phenoxyacetates because of difference in Ka values for different phenoxy acids. The values of k_{obs} estimated in this way were sufficient for evaluation of k'' for each L, but these k_{obs} values could not be compared for different phenoxyacetate ligands. Hence, [HL] was kept constant in the second series of experiments by adjusting the concentration of NH₄L so as to get [HL] = 0.05 M at pH 4.6. Therefore, in this series of experiments when [HL] for each ligand was kept constant at 0.05 M, the values of k'_{obs} thus obtained for different phenoxyacetates under these conditions could be correlated to the reaction constant ρ_3 for the general reaction (4) as follows :

$$\log k'_{obs} = \log k'_{obs(o)} + \sigma \rho_3 \quad (5)$$

where k'_{obs} implies for the pseudo-first order rate constant for the substituted phenoxyacetic acid with substituent constant σ and $k'_{obs(o)}$ is that for the unsubstituted parent phenoxyacetic acid. In case when [L⁻] was *p*-methoxyphenoxyacetate ion, the precipitation of HL (acid) occurred at pH 4.6, and hence the reaction with this ligand was studied at pH 6.00, to avoid precipitation.

Now, k_{obs} was determined as per usual at this pH and thereafter k'' was calculated (k'' is independent of pH as seen from eq. (3)). Now, from this value of k'' , k_{obs} (the first series of experiments) and k'_{obs} (the second series of experiments) both were again calculated at pH 4.6 using eq. (3).

It was estimated that at pH 6.00, more than 50% of the complex species (A) would exist as *cis*-[Co(en)₂(H₂O)(OH)]²⁺ (complex A'), the p*K*_a value of (A) being about 5.98 at 30 °C which is very close to the literature value at 25 °C (6.1)¹⁷. In spite of this, the calculation of k_{obs} and k'_{obs} values at pH 4.6 from the k_{obs} value at pH 6.00 may be justified from the following considerations.

Under the conditions of the large excess of *p*-methoxyphenoxyacetate ion (*p*-MPAA⁻), the reaction of the complex species (A) may be anticipated to follow the pseudo-first order pathways (Scheme 1). The equilibria (a) and (b) in this scheme involve proton transfer and hence these are attained very quickly. At constant pH

However, as the ammonium salts of ligands (NH₄L, L⁻ = phenoxyacetate anion) are used, the substitution reactions do not follow ion pairing mechanism as predicted for interaction of oxalic acid (H₂C₂O₄)²⁰.

A very little difference was observed between absorbance values of the solution of the complex species (A) at pH 4.6 and at 6.00, whereas there was practically no difference in the absorbance values of the solution of species (B) at these pH-values. The value of $k_{(\text{obs})}$ at pH 6.00 was determined from the slope of plot of $\log(D_{\infty} - D_0)/(D_{\infty} - D_t)$ versus time (*t*). Further, since D_0 values of A and A' are nearly the same and D_{∞} values of B and B' are identical at pH 4.6 and 6.00, the sum of $k_{1(\text{obs})}$ and $k_{2(\text{obs})}$ (Schemes 1 and 2) is slightly different from composite k_{obs} , but this

Scheme 1

6.00, the ratios; A : A' and B : B' remain constant during entire substitution process, but the total concentrations (amounts) of the reactants (A + A') decreases whereas the total concentration of the products (B + B') increases with time. In view of these considerations, the net reaction can be represented as in Scheme 2.

Scheme 2

difference observed was beyond any significant limit [i.e. $k_{(\text{obs})} \approx k_{1(\text{obs})} + k_{2(\text{obs})}$] at pH 4.6. This happened when it was calculated from the composite $k_{(\text{obs})}$ value of pH 6.00 due to change in the absorbance values of A and A', and those of B and B', at these two pH values. The value of k_{obs} at pH 4.6 was found to be different from that obtained at pH 6.00 because of the change in [H⁺] only.

The reaction $\text{A}^{3+} \rightarrow \text{B}^{2+}$ has been anticipated to be faster than the reaction $\text{A}'^{2+} \rightarrow \text{B}'^{1+}$ because the affinity of the *p*-MPAA⁻ in the tripolymeric A³⁺ is expected to be more facile than that its entry to the dipolymeric species B²⁺. The reaction constant (ρ) determines the sensitivity of the reactions due to the change in the electron density at the active site of ligand anion and depends on the nature, number and position of substituent in the benzene nucleus, irrespective of the host ion A or B, the difference in the

two rates will not produce any difference in the ρ -values of the two reactions.

Structure-activity-correlations :

In the series of phenoxyacetic acid herbicides, some of them are active whereas others are inactive²¹. The reactivity of these phenoxy acids depends on the nature, number and position of substituents in the benzene ring. The effect of substituents on the rate constant for the substitution reactions has also been examined by performing regression analysis for the linear correlation between k_{obs} and Hammett substituent constants (σ)²². The rate constant (k_{obs}) for the substitution reaction of the *cis*-complex-A with any substituted phenoxy acetic acid and that ($k_{\text{obs}(o)}$) for the substitution reaction with parent phenoxyacetic acid are related by the Hammett equation $\log k/k_0 = \sigma\rho$, where σ is the substituent constant and ρ is the reaction constant.

The linear correlations between $\log K_a$ values of different phenoxyacetic acids in 60% (v/v) dioxan and at 30 °C against the corresponding σ -values is observed (Fig. 1, $r = 0.88$). The slope of the plot $\log K_a$ vs σ gives a reaction constant $\rho_1 = 0.82$ by least squares method for the dissociation of phenoxyacetic acids under these conditions [reaction (1)]. The plot (Fig. 2) of $\log k''$ values for different phenoxyacetic acids against σ -values of the respective ligands is also found to be linear ($r = 0.82$). The reaction constant ρ_2 for reaction (2) as estimated from its slope, is found to be, -1.03 by least squares method. Further, the plot $\log k'_{\text{obs}}$ versus σ -values of the corresponding phenoxyacetates for the composite reaction

Fig. 1. Correlation between pK_a values of phenoxyacetic acids and Hammett substituent constants (σ).

(4) is also found to be linear with the slope -0.21 (ρ_3) by least squares method.

Fig. 2. Correlation between rate constants (k) and Hammett substituent constants (σ): $\log k$ vs σ (-o-o-); $\log k'$ vs σ (-□-□-□-) and $\log k''$ vs σ (-Δ-Δ-Δ-).

It is observed that ρ_3 (-0.21) for the composite reaction (4) is equal to the algebraic sum of the reaction constants. ρ_1 (0.82) and ρ_2 (-1.03) for the component reactions (1) and (2), respectively. It is justified because from (3), it is possible to write.

$$\begin{aligned} \log k'_{\text{obs}} &= \log k'' + \log K_a + \log [\text{HL}]/[\text{H}^+] \\ &= \log k''_0 + \sigma\rho_2 + \log K_{a(o)} + \sigma\rho_1 \\ &\quad + \log [\text{HL}]/[\text{H}^+] \\ &= \log \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{k''_0 K_{a(o)} [\text{HL}]} + (\rho_1 + \rho_2)\sigma \quad (6) \end{aligned}$$

In the second series of experiments, for all reactions, $[\text{HL}]$ and $[\text{H}^+]$ were kept constant, and hence the first term in the right hand side of (6) is constant. Therefore, a comparison of (5) and (6) gives $\rho_3 = \rho_1 + \rho_2$.

The negative value of reaction constant (ρ) for the series of reactions studied here has proved that the reactions are favoured ($k > k_0$) in the case of ligands having negative values of substituent constants (σ) whereas these are not in the favour ($k_0 > k$) for the ligands having positive σ -values in comparison to unsubstituted ligand. Alternatively, the reactions with negative ρ -values are favoured by high electron density at the reaction site of

the co-ordinating ligand (σ -negative) and, therefore, it should follow SN^2 -mechanism. The large negative value of ρ_2 (-1.03) indicates that the reactions of (A) with unsubstituted or substituted phenoxyacetate ions follow SN^2 -mechanism. Also, it is to be emphasized that there are examples²¹ of reactions for which ρ -values are found to be high negative which are in agreement to the ρ_2 value (-1.03) observed in the present investigation.

Conclusion :

From above discussion, it is evident that phenoxyacetic acid herbicides form stable ternary metal complexes through substitution reactions but rate constant data both for biologically inactive (PAA) and active (*p*-OHPAA, *p*-ClPAA, etc.) are of comparable magnitude. These observations, thus, lend further support to the view that complexation may not be the possible mode of action of phenoxyacetic acid herbicides.

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